
Study to Assess the Knowledge Regarding Hypertension among Adults of Selected Rural Community**Poonam Sharma Assistant Professor III Amity University****Haryana, Gurgaon****2) Rebecca Dillu Assistant Professor I****(Obstetrics and Gynaecological Nursing) Amity University****Haryana, Gurgaon****ABSTRACT**

Background: *Blood pressure is the force exerted by the blood against the walls of blood vessels, and the magnitude of this force depends on the cardiac output and the resistance of the blood vessels. Hypertension is defined as having a blood pressure higher than 140 over 90 mmHg. High blood pressure affects millions -- even children and teens.*

Aim: *A descriptive study was conducted in a selected village named Holi. at district Ambala, Haryana with an objective to assess the knowledge regarding hypertension among adults and to find out the association of knowledge of adults regarding hypertension with selected variables*

Methodology: *Survey approach and descriptive research design was used to conduct the present study. Convenience sampling technique was used to select the sample size of 100 adults who were between the age group of 30-50 years. Knowledge of study sample regarding concept, risk factors, signs and symptoms, prevention, control, complication and treatment of hypertension were assessed through self-administered questionnaire.*

Results: *The study findings revealed that more than half respondents (62%) had poor knowledge score, 36% had average knowledge, and very few (2%) had good knowledge while none of the sample had excellent knowledge regarding hypertension. The level of knowledge of the selected sample was significantly associated with their educational status and dietary salt intake.*

Conclusion: *Since the study showed that maximum adults had poor knowledge regarding hypertension so the nurses are in key position to educate the people about various aspects of hypertension through public awareness programme to improve their health status and bring down the rate of mortality and morbidity among the population.*

Keywords: *Adults, hypertension, knowledge.*

INTRODUCTION

Health of an individual is conceptually different in different countries, in the same country at different times and in same individuals at different ages. It is thus a relative and not an absolute state¹.

Hypertension is becoming a public health emergency worldwide, especially in developing countries, where studies projected an increase by 80% in the number of hypertensive by the year 2025. Hypertension is controllable disease and a small decline in 2mm of Hg population wide in BP can prevent 1, 51,000 stroke cases².

High blood pressure means that the heart is working harder than normal, putting both the heart and blood vessels under strain. Blood pressure is the force of blood against the wall of arteries³.

Mild hypertension is when the systolic blood pressure ranges between 140 and 160 mm of Hg and diastolic ranges between 90 and 100 mm of Hg. Moderate hypertension is when systolic blood pressure ranges between 100 and 120 mm of Hg. Severe hypertension is when the systolic blood pressure is above 200 mm Hg and diastolic pressure is above 120 mm of Hg⁴.

Cardiovascular diseases have emerged as an important health problem in India. High blood pressure (BP) is a major risk factor and better control can lead to prevention of 300,000 of the 1.5 million annual deaths from cardiovascular diseases in India⁵.

Studies have shown a high prevalence of hypertension in both urban and rural areas. Subsequent studies report steadily increasing hypertension prevalence- 4.35% in Agra (1961), 6.43% in Rohtak (1975), 15.52% in Mumbai (1980), 14.08% in Ludhiana (1985), 10.99% in Jaipur (1995), 11.59% in Delhi (1997), 13.1% in Chandigarh (1999)².

The prevalence of hypertension ranges from 20-40% in urban adults and 12-17% among rural adults. The number of people with hypertension is projected to increase from 118 million in 2000 to 214 million in 2025 with nearly equal to number of men and women⁶.

A research study revealed that a majority of the rural population in India has inadequate access to healthcare and regular screening for hypertension is not practiced. Almost every third person is suffering from this condition and may be related to modern lifestyle and food habits (stress, hereditary, excess salt intake, lack of exercises, sedentary life style, smoking and excess alcoholism)⁶. Maintaining a reasonable weight is very important in minimizing the risk for hypertension. People who are overweight, even a small loss in weight also leads to reduction in high blood pressure⁷. For sodium sensitive people, reducing sodium is a good approach in reducing the risk for hypertension. The recommendation of dietary intake of sodium is 1,500 to 2,300 mg in a day⁸.

A study assessed the effect of a programme of resistance training on central blood pressure and arterial stiffness in 17 men and women aged 65-78 years. Following 20 weeks of training, systolic and diastolic pressure is reduced by 6 and 3 mm of Hg and small change in arterial stiffness⁹. A researcher concluded that regular exercise help in reducing blood pressure and left hypertrophy in African- American men with severe hypertension. It was found that after 16 weeks mean diastolic blood pressure had decreased to normal in patients who exercised⁹.

Hypertension is called as a silent killer since it has no warning signs and symptoms that's why it's very dangerous ailment and it is the main risk factor of strokes, coronary heart diseases and cardio vascular

diseases in India¹⁰. Therefore the adults need to know about promotive and preventive strategies regarding hypertension in order to improve their physiological and psychological well-being and to prevent complications. So this study aims to assess the knowledge and to educate adults to enhance their knowledge regarding hypertension.

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the knowledge regarding hypertension among adults.
2. To find out the association of knowledge of adults regarding hypertension with selected variables.

METHODOLOGY

In this study Survey research approach and descriptive research design were used to collect the data from the sample size of 100 adults who were between the age of 30- 50 years, who could speak and read Hindi and were willing to participate in the study. The study was conducted in the selected rural area of community (village Holi) Ambala, Haryana.

Convenience sampling technique was used to select the study sample and self-administered structured knowledge questionnaire was used to collect the data from adults. The questionnaire comprised of two sections; section first had questions related to personal variables (age, gender, religion, educational status, marital status, occupation, type of job, monthly income, personal history, dietary habits, dietary salt intake, physical activity, history of any disease, type of family and family history of blood pressure) while section two consisted of questions about knowledge regarding hypertension classified under various areas like concept of hypertension; risk factors and causes; signs and symptoms; prevention and control of hypertension; complications and treatment.

To ensure the content validity of the tool (structured questionnaire), it was submitted to nine experts (eight nursing experts and one cardiologist). Reliability of the tool was computed by using Kudler-Richardson formula. The reliability of structured knowledge questionnaire was found to be 0.7. Since the normal range is 0.5- 0.9 so the tool was found to be reliable.

Ethical approval was taken from the Sarpanch of the village to conduct the study. Written informed Consent was taken for the study sample regarding their willingness to participate in the research study and the purpose for carrying out research study was explained to the participants. Confidentiality of the information of the sample was maintained.

Data was analyzed by descriptive and inferential statistics i.e. frequency and percentage distribution, mean percentage, median and chi square to determine the association between knowledge with selected variables.

RESULT

Frequency and percentage distribution of adults according to their personal variables revealed that most (46%) of the adults were between the age group of 41-45 years, more than half (57%) were female, majority (95%) of the sample belonged to Hindu religion, 32% had educational background till

middle school, majority (95%) of the adults were married, 42% of the sample were unemployed, most (60%) of the sample had sedentary job, approximately half (54%) of the adults had family income between the range of Rs. 5001- 10000, most of the sample were vegetarian, majority(80%) of the adults had normal salt intake in their diet, maximum (63%) didn't involve in physical activity, 26% of the sample had history of heart disease, approximately half (57%) of the sample belonged to nuclear family, maximum (74%) had family history of blood pressure.

TABLE 1

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Adults as Per as their Knowledge Score Regarding Hypertension

N= 100

Level of knowledge score	Range of knowledge score	Frequency (%)
Excellent	>27	0
Good	24-27	02
Average	19-23	36
Below average	0-18	62

Maximum score: 36 ; Minimum score: 0

Table 1 reveals that the more than half respondents (62%) had below average knowledge, 36% of the adults had average knowledge while very few (2%) had good knowledge regarding hypertension and none of adult had excellent knowledge regarding hypertension.

TABLE 2
Mean, Median and Standard Deviation of Knowledge Scores among Adults Regarding Hypertension on Structured Knowledge Questionnaire

N= 100

	Mean	Median	SD	Range of Score
Knowledge score	17.11	17.5	3.81	0

Maximum score= 36

Minimum Score= 0

The data presented in Table 2 reveals that the mean knowledge score of adults regarding hypertension was 17.11, median was 17.5 and standard deviation was 3.81 with maximum score of 36 and minimum score of 0.

TABLE 3
Area wise Mean, Mean% of Knowledge Score Obtained by Adults on a Structured Knowledge Questionnaire

N= 100

S.No,	Areas	Maximum Score	Mean Score	Mean%
1.	Concept	3	0.79	26.33
2.	Risk factor and causes	6	2.64	44
3.	Sign and symptoms	4	1.81	45.25
4.	Prevention and control	11	6.29	51.18
5.	Treatment and complication	12	5.53	46.08

Maximum score= 36

Minimum Score= 0

The data presented in table 3 depicts the mean and mean percentage of knowledge score obtained by adults in five areas. The highest mean percentage of knowledge score (51.18%) was in the area of prevention and control followed by treatment and complication (46.08%). The mean percentage of signs and symptoms was 45.25%, risk factor and causes had mean percentage of 44% while the lowest mean percentage was in the area of concept of hypertension. This data indicates that the selected adults had very less knowledge regarding the concept of hypertension while they had more knowledge in the area of prevention and control of hypertension.

Association of knowledge score of adults with selected personal variables was computed by using inferential statistics i.e. Chi square which revealed that there is a significant association of knowledge score with educational status and dietary salt intake of the selected sample.

CONCLUSION

Hypertension is one of the most common lifestyle diseases today, with every third person having suffering from it.. The fact is that in 90% patients there is no known cause for hypertension and this makes it even more to be alert. Most are not even aware that they have hypertension, which makes the scenario rather grim. Therefore people should be made aware about the hypertension right from the childhood till they get elderly. The study concluded that more than the half study sample had below average knowledge and very few (2%) were having good knowledge while none of the sample had excellent knowledge regarding various aspects of hypertension. The study also revealed that there was significant association of knowledge score with the educational status and dietary intake of salt by study sample. Since hypertension is a silent killer which doesn't have specific therefore the health care providers are in a very key position to educate the children, adolescents, adults and the elderly people regarding hypertension, its risk factors and causes, its signs and symptoms, prevention, prevention and control of hypertension so that the complications (including fatality) can be prevented.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

It is a great privilege to express our special gratitude to the Sarpanch of the village (Holi) for granting permission to conduct our research study and thus facilitating the execution of the study.

We wish to extend our heartfelt thanks with much appreciation for our study sample for their willingness and full cooperation in participating in our research study and for their honest information without which it would have been impossible to complete this study.

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